

NUCLEATION AND GROWTH IN COLD-ROLLED ALUMINIUM
CONTAINING SILICON CARBIDE WHISKERS AND ALUMINIUM OXIDE PARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

The recrystallization behaviour has been studied in silicon carbide (SiC) whisker (1-4 vol.%) reinforced aluminium composites. The materials contain 0.8 vol.% fine aluminium oxide particles (Al_2O_3) and has been deformed by cold rolling to 90% reduction in thickness. The microstructure in the early stage of recrystallization and after the completion of recrystallization was examined by transmission and scanning electron microscopy, and light microscopy. It was found that the SiC whiskers, often present in groups, showed a strong tendency to stimulate nucleation and to accelerate the recrystallization whereas the Al_2O_3 particles had the opposite effect. It was found that with increasing concentration of silicon carbide whiskers and with increasing annealing temperature the recrystallized grain size decreased.

INTRODUCTION

Aluminium matrix composites reinforced with SiC whiskers or particulates are now emerging as important structural materials. The fabrication methods and mechanical properties of silicon carbide reinforced aluminium composites have been widely studied. However, the effect of thermomechanical processing on the microstructure has only been investigated to a limited extent. The effect of SiC on the recrystallization of Al-0.8 vol.% Al_2O_3 have been studied in detail for an alloy containing 2 vol.% SiC [1]. It was shown that the presence of SiC affects the entire recrystallization process but especially the nucleation as groups of SiC are preferential nucleation sites. The volume concentration of SiC might therefore be an important parameter in controlling the recrystallization. In the present work the study was extended by examining alloys with 1 and 4 vol.% SiC. Besides the actual vol.% SiC the materials and the experimental techniques were identical to those in Reference 1, and the results are therefore directly comparable. This allows a discussion in the present paper of the effect of SiC varied from 1 to 4 vol.% on the recrystallization in Al-0.8 vol.% Al_2O_3 .

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Manufacturing of Materials

The atomized aluminium powder (mean particle diameter $6.4 \mu m$) containing 0.8 vol.% Al_2O_3 , 0.26 wt% Fe and 0.18 wt% Si was used as composite matrix. SiC whiskers made by Tokai Carbon Co. Ltd. Japan were used as fibre reinforcement. They consisted of β -type (cube) SiC single crystals 0.1-1.0 μm in diameter and 30-100 μm in length. The products examined were manufactured from aluminium powder with 1, 2 and 4 vol.% SiC whiskers respectively by blending, compacting and extrusion [1]. The final cold deformation prior to the recrystallization treatment was 90 % cold rolling reduction in thickness parallel to the original extrusion direction. For comparative purposes, an Al- Al_2O_3 alloy was made from atomized aluminium powder by a similar technique [2].

2. Particle Parameters

The diameter of as-received SiC whiskers was measured by SEM. The SiC whiskers were fragmented during processing. The length of individual SiC whiskers in 90 % cold-rolled materials was also measured. The spacial distribution of SiC whiskers in 90 % cold-rolled sheet was fairly uniform and highly aligned along the rolling (extrusion) direction. However, a large fraction of the SiC whiskers existed in groups of size ranging from 0.5 μm to 5 μm , and particle distance within SiC groups was generally less than 0.5 μm . The dimension and inter-particle spacing of SiC whiskers and Al_2O_3 particles are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Structural parameters

Al_2O_3			SiC			
Volume fraction (%)	Diameter* of equivalent sphere (nm)	Particle* spacing (μm)	Volume fraction (%)	Diameter (μm)	Length 90% cold-rolled (μm)	Particle [§] spacing (μm)
0.8	31	0.23	1	0.54	-	4.8
			2		2.0	3.4
			4		-	2.4

* Ref. [2]

§ Ref. [1]

3. Experiment

The recrystallization behaviour of the 90 % cold-rolled Al- Al_2O_3 -SiC composites and Al- Al_2O_3 alloy was followed by macro-hardness measurements after isochronal annealing treatments. The temperature needed to achieve 50% recrystallization was determined. The initial and recrystallized grain size was measured. The nucleation behaviour was studied in two of the materials namely the Al- Al_2O_3 -SiC composite containing 2 vol.% SiC and in the Al- Al_2O_3 material. The nuclei sizes were measured as diameter of areas of low dislocation density, partly or entirely surrounded by high-angle boundaries.

RESULTS

1. Nucleation and Growth

TEM examination revealed that the number density of recrystallization nuclei was higher in 90 % cold-rolled Al- Al_2O_3 -2% SiC alloy than in Al- Al_2O_3 material [1]. The nuclei in Al- Al_2O_3 -2 vol.% SiC alloy were found to be connected with large SiC fibres or fibre groups. Figure 1(a) shows one of the nuclei at its early stage, and a well developed nucleus can be seen in Fig. 1(b). The average size of the nuclei was approximately 3 μm . Subgrain growth was observed frequently at the interface of SiC fibres and aluminium matrix. However, only a few of these large subgrains developed into nuclei. Fine particle pinning of subgrain boundaries was seen clearly. The nuclei in Al- Al_2O_3 alloy were associated with large particles (iron aluminium intermetallics) and high angle boundaries. These observations are in good agreement with the results reported for an alloy of Al-0.6 vol.% Al_2O_3 [3]. The average size of nuclei was about 10 μm .

The temperatures of nucleation as determined by TEM are given in Table 2. These temperatures represent the lowest at which potential nuclei were found to form within one hour. The temperatures for 50 % recrystallization were determined and are given in Table 2. It was found that the recrystallization temperature decreased significantly with the addition of 1 vol.% SiC, whereas the effect of increasing the SiC content was small.

Table 2
Temperature of nucleation and of 50 % recrystallization

	Al-Al ₂ O ₃	Al-Al ₂ O ₃ 1 vol.% SiC	Al-Al ₂ O ₃ 2 vol.% SiC	Al-Al ₂ O ₃ 4vol.% SiC
Temperature of nucleation (°C)	397	-	300	-
Temperature of 50 % recrystallization (°C)	435	332	325	325

In Al-Al₂O₃ material, the number of nuclei was very low and the spacial distribution of nuclei was inhomogeneous. It was frequently observed in this alloy that in some areas the recrystallization was complete, whereas in other areas the structure was almost unchanged compared to the deformed state. The growth in the rolling direction was faster than in the transverse and sheet normal directions. In contrast, nucleation in the Al-Al₂O₃-2 vol.% SiC alloy was more frequent and quite random; and growth was more uniform in the rolling plane although the growth was still restricted in the sheet normal direction. The recrystallization behaviour of these two alloys is illustrated schematically in Fig. 2. The number of recrystallized grains per unit area in the rolling plane was measured for both alloys during annealing at 310°C (Al-Al₂O₃-2 vol.% SiC) and 420°C (Al-Al₂O₃). The result is shown in Fig. 2. It was found that within the first 100 min of annealing, the number density of recrystallized grain forming was similar in both alloys, but between 100 and 120 min, there was a much more rapid increase in the Al-Al₂O₃-SiC alloy compared to the Al-Al₂O₃ alloy; after 120 min annealing, the grain number/unit area remained almost constant for both materials.

2. Recrystallized Grains

The initial and recrystallized grain sizes in the Al-Al₂O₃-SiC composites and Al-Al₂O₃ alloy are given in Table 3. The histograms of the frequency distribution of recrystallized grain sizes in all the materials are shown in Fig. 3. Compared to the Al-Al₂O₃ alloy, the recrystallized grain size in Al-Al₂O₃-2 vol.% SiC decreased and the size distribution became more narrow. Although the grains in these two materials were pancake-shaped, the grains in the Al-Al₂O₃-2 vol.% SiC composite were more equiaxed when studied in the rolling plane (Fig. 3). The variation of SiC content from 1 to 4 vol.% did not have obvious effect on the grain shape, but did reduce the grain size as it is shown in Table 3 when the same annealing temperature (400°C) is applied. The size distribution became sharper and shifted to the lower end with increasing content of SiC. Furthermore, it was found that the recrystallized grain size in the Al-Al₂O₃-2 vol.% SiC and Al-Al₂O₃ alloys decreased and the size distribution became more narrow with increasing annealing temperature (see Fig. 4).

Table 3
Grain size* of starting and recrystallized materials

	Initial grain size	Recrystallized grain size (90% cold-rolled)
	(μm)	(μm)
Al-Al ₂ O ₃	1116±113	829±186 (420°C)
		443± 59 (493°C)
Al-Al ₂ O ₃ -1% SiC	742± 67	234± 10 (400°C)
Al-Al ₂ O ₃ -2% SiC	560± 42	435± 25 (310°C)
		236± 9 (355°C)
		154± 5 (400°C)
		92± 3 (420°C)
Al-Al ₂ O ₃ -4% SiC	390± 19	96± 3 (400°C)

* The measured grain size was the mean diameter of the equivalent circle grain in the rolling plane. The annealing temperature is given in parentheses.

DISCUSSION

Comparing the nucleation behaviour of Al-Al₂O₃-SiC to the Al-Al₂O₃ alloy, it is found that the presence of SiC fibres leads to a decrease in the critical nuclei size and to an increase in the density of nuclei. The Al₂O₃ particles, as analyzed in ref. [3], significantly increase the critical nuclei size and reduce the density of nuclei compared to Al without Al₂O₃. It is therefore suggested that the nucleation behaviour of Al-Al₂O₃-SiC composite material is a result of a combined effect of SiC fibres and Al₂O₃ particles.

The present work indicates that SiC fibre groups have higher capacity to stimulate nuclei as compared with single fibres. This can be attributed to the size and shape effect of SiC groups, which produce a large local increase in dislocation density and misorientation during deformation. However, the fibre group are not such potent nucleation sites as would be expected. A calculation shows that in the 90 % cold-rolled Al-Al₂O₃-2% SiC alloy the concentration of SiC groups which may be potential nucleation sites is about two orders of magnitude larger than the concentration of nuclei which grow into recrystallized grains during annealing at 355°C. The relatively small concentration of nuclei may have several causes. The strong pinning effect of Al₂O₃ particles on the substructure [4] may reduce considerably the capacity of SiC fibres to stimulate nucleation and therefore reduce the number of nucleation sites. Furthermore, the nuclei formed at SiC fibres might impinge against other fibres and particles and stop growing before they are above the critical size. As a result of the combined effect of SiC fibres and Al₂O₃ particles, the number of effective nuclei is reduced and the recrystallized microstructure contains a number of very small grains (see Fig. 3). Such very small grains are also present in the Al-Al₂O₃ alloy.

The introduction of SiC fibres into Al/Al₂O₃ leads to a decrease in grain size and a narrowing of the grain size distribution. This consequence of adding fibres on grain size is enhanced with increasing volume concentration of SiC fibres. This may be related to the effect of the fibre concentration on nucleation density which significantly increases with increasing concentration of fibres (or fibre groups). The fibres may also affect the growth rate which may be reduced when the fibre concentration is increased. As a net result the average grain size is decreased especially due to a reduction of the size of the large grains. Thus the grain size distribution will become more narrow.

An increase in nucleation density and a decrease in growth rate with increasing concentration of SiC fibres may also explain the observation that the recrystallization temperature is almost unaffected by an increase in the concentration of SiC fibres from 1 to 4 vol. %.

The recrystallized grain size is significantly affected by the temperature in the Al-Al₂O₃-SiC composites and Al-Al₂O₃ alloy. This effect has also been observed in Al-Si alloys [5] containing a mixture of fine and coarse particles. Tentative explanations have been given for this phenomenon, but further investigations are necessary.

In summary the recrystallized grain size of Al-Al₂O₃-SiC composites is a complex function of materials parameter and processing variables. An optimization is therefore possible to obtain microstructures, which will have a beneficial effect on the mechanical properties [6].

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Fig. 1. Nuclei formed at SiC fibres.

Fig. 2. Number density of recrystallized grains as a function of annealing time. The recrystallization microstructure development is also illustrated schematically.

Fig. 3. Histograms of the frequency distribution of recrystallized grain sizes after one hour annealing. (a) Al-Al₂O₃, 493°C. (b) Al-Al₂O₃-1 vol.% SiC, 400°C. (c) Al-Al₂O₃-2 vol.% SiC, 400°C. (d) Al-Al₂O₃-4 vol.% SiC, 400°C.

Fig. 4. Recrystallized grain size as a function of annealing temperature.